

Degradation Status of Certain Urban Lakes of Coimbatore, India

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the award of the Degree of Master of Science in Environmental Science*

By

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DEDICATED TO

My

Mother

Father

Teachers

&

The Almighty

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List of Abbreviations

$\mu\text{S/cm}$	micro Siemens per centimeter, equivalent to micro mho
Alk.	Alkalinity
BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand
d	Dominance value
D	Simpson Diversity Index (Simpson 1949)
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
EC	Electrical Conductivity
ETM+	Enhanced Thematic Mapper
GLCF	Global Land Cover Facility
H	Shannon Wiener Diversity Index (Shannon and Wiener 1963)
H ₂ S	Hydrogen Sulphide
IFOV	Instantaneous Field Of View
J	Evenness Index (Hill 1973)
mg/l	milligram per liter otherwise parts per million
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
NO ₂	Nitrite
ORP	Oxidation Reduction Potential
P	Significant value
PCA	Principle Component Analysis
pH	Hydrogen Ion concentration
PO ₄	Phosphate
S	Family Richness
SO ₄	Sulphate
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
TM	Landsat Thematic Mapper
WQI	Water Quality Index
WRS	World Reference System

SUMMARY

Urbanization has profound long-lasting impact on lakes and leads to the total retardation of the ecosystem. This complex and dynamic problem needs in depth understanding before the implementation of conservation or mitigation measures. As an initial step, the present study was carried out during 2008-2009 on typical four urban lakes of Coimbatore, India which are facing threats from varying degrees of urbanization and related anomalies. Physico-chemical analyses of lakes water revealed that the increased degradation in water quality was observed in those lakes which were in close proximity with the urban centers. Ukkadam lake was suffered highest degradation showing Water Quality Index (WQI) of 123, followed by Kurchi lake (WQI=97), Chinnakulam lake (WQI=84) and Perur lake (WQI=75). However, a slight different trend was observed in the case of littoral benthic fauna of these lakes. Diversity indices and community composition of benthic fauna were used as an indicator of degradation status of the lakes studied. Shannon Wiener diversity for macro-invertebrates was highest in Chinnakulam lake ($H=2.2531$) followed by Perur lake ($H=2.0771$), Kurchi lake ($H=2.0636$) and Ukkadam lake ($H=1.2141$). Land use changes and spatial analysis carried out in geographical area of these lakes using Landsat satellite temporal imagery indicated that there was an unprecedented increase in urban area (more than 50%) during 1989-1999. Spatial analyses using Landsat imagery also gave the similar results as that by water quality. From all these analyses it is understood that these lakes are facing varying degrees of pressures due to urbanization and require immediate implementation of conservation and management plans before such threats turn into irreparable / irreversible impacts.

Chapter 1.

INTRODUCTION

Sustaining a wide variety of biota, influencing local climate and hydrology make wetlands a productive ecosystem on earth (Whittaker 1971, Adams and Stockwell 1983). Lake / wetlands (Reddy 2004) have natural and anthropogenic origin. People constructed lakes in downstream of rivers as a source of portable water, food resources, irrigation, recreation and waste disposal (Beeton 2002). During ancient days, lakes were constructed mainly for storing potable water and for irrigation purposes. This essential functionality makes societies to safeguard the well being of lakes ecosystem. But in long time this crucial need was circumvented by urbanization and related anomalies thus resulting into unsuitable drinking water. Thus, lakes once used for water resources are rapidly changing ironically into waste water storage tanks and waste dumping sites. Urban lakes are wilderness centers in concrete jungles and undergoing rapid degradation throughout the country (Reddy 2004). Such degradation is a cause of urbanization, industrialization, agricultural effluent discharges, municipal waste dumping and hydro geomorphic changes of canals and river linking projects. It is observed that urbanization has long lasting impact on the aquatic ecosystems along with total retardation of the system (Booth and Jackson 1997). This dynamic and complex problem makes conservation and mitigation efforts ineffective in their goal and needs further understanding. The monitoring and assessment of the lakes may give a better understanding about the potential causes of degradation.

Assessment of the physico-chemical variables of water (Burden *et al.* 2002) and their continuous monitoring gives insight into the seasonal and temporal changes in water quality. The aquatic organisms having close relationship with their ecosystems are the best indicator of habitat quality / status (Mandaville 2002). Their prevalence is based on habitat conditions which are determined by water quality, habitat structure, energy source, flow regime and biotic interaction factors (Ramakrishnan 2003). Assessment of these aquatic organisms especially in urbanized wetlands and also those which are facing varying degrees of anthropogenic pressures in their immediate vicinity may help revealing the systems functionality and its status.

The spatial occurrence of these sediment dwellers, their crucial role in linking producers and top carnivores and their intermediate life span make them potential indicators of water quality and ecosystem functioning. The conventional physico-chemical methods praised for their specificity and accuracy may not address the holistic condition of ecosystem and are generally expensive. The level of degradation of water resources can be more precisely quantified by bio-monitoring methodology using above said bio-indicators.

The multi-temporal and multi-spectral satellite imagery gives an extensive opportunity in assessing the temporal changes in land cover and land use pattern. It gives an insight about how the land use characters such as urban sprawl and reduction in vegetation and other land use characters change over time. Thus, by integrating the land use classification along with spatial analysis one can acquire a better understanding of the status of urban area influence zones on sensitive ecosystems and it's likely spreading out in future.

OBJECTIVES

In view of the above facts, the present study was undertaken in Coimbatore to accomplish the following objectives.

1. Biological assessment of wetlands using benthic macro-invertebrates as pollution indicator.
2. Assessment of the seasonal variations in the physico-chemical properties of wetlands of Coimbatore.
3. Assessment of the land use, land cover change of Coimbatore lakes and get information about urban influence zones on these lakes.

Chapter 2.

STUDY AREA

The present study was undertaken at Coimbatore, an important industrial city of India, ranking 11th in terms of population, located in the state of Tamil Nadu, between 10°55' and 11°10'N, and 77°10' and 76°50'E at an approximate altitude of 470m. The Noyyal river system feeds around 15,974 acres of agricultural lands existing in and around the city through 28 lakes (Mohanraj *et al.* 2000). The river during lean months goes dry, thus, serving as a dumping yard for garbage and industrial wastes.

Major portion of lakes fed by river Noyyal lie in and around the urban areas. Due to population outgrowth, the lakes are extensively exploited for befitting the needs for drinking purpose, water storage facilities for agriculture, aqua culture, ground water refilling, etc. These wetlands are facing point source pollution (effluent discharges from industry and drainage systems) and non-point source pollution (agricultural lands and urban settlements). The nutrient load is leading to eutrophication of these wetlands thus, affecting their biodiversity. Such a rapid urbanization is leading to the degradation of lakes in Coimbatore hence, raising an issue of concern for their restoration and conservation.

The present study was conducted during May 2008 - February 2009 in four wetlands viz., Perur lake (L1), Kuruchi lake (L2), Ukkadam lake (L3) and Chinnakulam lake (L4) located within a geographical extent of 38 sq.km (Figure 1). The lakes existing in and around this area are facing varying degrees of degradation from urbanization, sewage and industrial effluent discharge, garbage dumping and agricultural activities.

Figure 1. Study area map

The Perur lake (L1, Figure 2) spreading 264.8 acres, attracts 77 avian species (Palaniappan, 2008). The encroachment area in this wetland is nearly 1.5 acres and comprises of 100 huts in the foreshore and 50 on surplus course in the bunds. It is surrounded by agricultural lands, villages and roads. One third of the wetland is colonized by *Acacia* sp. facilitating nesting of colonial birds.

The second study site, the Kuruchi lake (L2, Figure 3) has a water spread area of 343.96 acres and holds least water storage capacity because of its shallowness. The encroachment area in the tank is 9.50 acres with nearly 200 huts on the bund and 274 in the channel bank in the water-spread area.

Major portion of this lake remains polluted by *Eichhornia crassipes* throughout the year. This wetland receives municipal sewage and is a site for dumping garbage from human inhabitations around its vicinity.

The Ukkadam lake (L3, Figure 4) having largest water spread area among Coimbatore wetlands, is situated close to municipal market and bus stand. This wetland is the ultimate receiver of various industrial effluents, urban sewage and municipal solid wastes. Although, formerly large quantity of solid waste was dumped along its banks, recently, the quantity of solid waste dump has reduced considerably. The area containing 15 huts on the bund and 20 on the supply channel bank comprises nearly 0.35 acres. Seasonally, the wetland is covered with dense mats of *Eichhornia crassipes* and other hydrophytes. This wetland was known to attract several migratory birds.

Chinnakulam lake (L4, Figure 5) has a shallow long stretch of water spread area which goes discontinuous during lean months. Very recently (February 2009) municipal garbage dumping area present in the eastern part of this lake was separated from garbage dumping by fencing. The symbols with yellow colour are only water sampling sites. However, symbols with red colour are water as well as benthic macro-invertebrates sampling sites (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 2. Study site - Perur lake (L1).

Figure 3. Study site - Kuruchi lake (L2).

Figure 4. Study site - Ukkadam lake (L3).

Figure 5. Study site - Chinnakulam lake (L4).

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ASSESSMENT**Sampling and Processing**

Surface water samples were collected from five sites at each lake (Perur, Kuruchi, Ukkadam and Chinnakulam) during 4 seasons viz. summer (May 2008), monsoon (August 2008), post-monsoon (November 2008), and winter (February 2009). Aliquots of surface water samples were grabbed at a horizontal distance of approximately 500m intervals in each wetland and transferred in pre-treated / laboratory cleaned bottles, labeled, and transferred to ice boxes with frozen gel packs. The samples were then transferred to the laboratory, stored at 4°C in dark till further processing and analysis. Physico-chemical parameters namely pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS, mg/l), Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD, mg/l), alkalinity (mg/l), chlorides (mg/l), phosphates (mg/l), sulphate (mg/l), ammonia nitrogen (mg/l), and nitrate nitrogen (mg/l) were examined following standard methods (APHA 1992, Saxena 1987). Specific methods for each parameter followed are discussed in subsequent paragraphs.

Sample Analysis**Hydrogen Ion Concentration (pH) and Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP, mV)**

pH is logarithmic reciprocal value of hydrogen ion concentration and is determined by measuring the electromotive force of a cell comprising an indicator electrode which is responsive to hydrogen ions and a reference electrode immersed in sample solution.

Chemical Reagents**Buffer solution**

A set of three buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2 were prepared by dissolving each commercially available buffer tablets in 100ml of distilled water. The resulting solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2 were stored in 100ml vials.

Procedure

The water sample was taken in a beaker and the pH was measured using the pH meter (Model-Digisun-7007). The pH meter was standardized by using set of buffer solutions (pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2). The electrode was dipped in to the sample and the pH value was read directly on digital display of the instrument. Values for Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP, mV) were also read directly from the same instrument.

Electrical Conductivity (EC, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)

It is a measure of the ability of the sample to carry electric current. It is measured based on conductance between spatially fixed anode and cathode immersed in water sample.

Chemical Reagents

Potassium Chloride (KCl) solution (0.01 N): Exactly 0.0745g potassium chloride was dissolved in a little distilled water in 100ml standard measuring flask and volume was made up to the mark using distilled water. The resulting solution was 0.01 N KCl that was used for standardizing both the conductivity and TDS meter.

Procedure

The electrical conductivity was measured using the digital conductivity meter (Digisun-D1-9009). The conductivity meter was standardized using 0.01N KCl solution. Electrode was washed with distilled water and dipped in the sample. The reading was noted down in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS, mg/l)

The dissolved solids in water are directly proportional to its dissolved mineral matter content.

Chemical Reagents

Potassium Chloride (KCl) solution (0.01 N): The details of the preparation have already been discussed in the EC section and the same was used.

Procedure

The instrument (Digital TDS meter, Model EI-651-E) was standardized using 0.01 N KCl solutions. The electrode was then cleaned with distilled water and immersed in the sample. The TDS values were recorded from the meter and were expressed in mg/l.

Chloride (mg/l)

It was determined by titrating sample containing chloride with silver nitrate which forms silver chloride in the presence of Potassium Chromate (as an indicator). The reaction imparts a colour change of sample from yellow to red precipitation.

Chemical Reagents

Silver nitrate solution (0.02N): Exactly 0.3397g silver nitrate solution was dissolved in 100ml distilled water.

Potassium chromate indicator: 1g of potassium chromate was dissolved in 20ml distilled water. To this, few drops of 0.02 N silver nitrate solution was added and kept for 12 hours. It was then filtered and diluted to 100 ml.

Procedure

10ml sample was taken in a beaker and to this 5-6 drops of potassium chromate solution were added. This was titrated against silver nitrate solution until persistent red brick colour appeared from initial yellow. The initial and final burette readings were recorded.

Alkalinity

The alkalinity of water is the capacity of hydroxyl ions and anions of weak acids to neutralize an equivalent amount of strong acids. It is determined by titrating sample with standard solution of mineral acid using pH indicators such as phenolphthalein and methyl orange.

Chemical Reagents

Sulphuric acid (0.02N): 2.8ml concentrated sulphuric acid was diluted to 1 litre using distilled

water. Exactly 200ml of this stock solution (0.1) was made to 1 litre using distilled water.

Phenolphthalein Indicator: Commercially available.

Methyl Orange Indicator: Commercially available.

Procedure

About 50ml sample was taken in a 100ml conical flask and 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added. Appearance of slight pink color in sample denoted phenolphthalein alkalinity which was titrated against (0.02 N) sulphuric acid until the pink colour disappeared. To the same sample 3 drops of methyl orange indicator was added and titrated against (0.02 N) sulphuric acid until the yellow colour of sample turned to orange. The initial and final burette readings were noted and total alkalinity was estimated by adding up the phenolphthalein and methyl orange alkalinity.

Total hardness (mg/l)

It is defined as the sum of the calcium concentration and magnesium concentration expressed in mg/l and is determined by titrating sample with EDTA in presence of Erichrome black-T as indicator. The initial wine red colour of sample turns into blue colour when all the calcium and magnesium ions in sample form chelates with EDTA.

Chemical Reagents

Ammonia buffer solution: About 13.5g Ammonium chloride was dissolved in 114ml concentrated ammonia solution and made up to 200ml using distilled water.

Erichrome black-T indicator: 0.5g Erichrome black-T was dissolved in 100ml of 80% Ethyl alcohol.

EDTA solution (0.01 N): Exactly 0.3723g EDTA was dissolved in 100ml distilled water.

Procedure

50ml of sample was taken in a 100ml conical flask. To this 1ml of Ammonia buffer solution and 4 drops of Erichrome black-T indicator was added and was titrated against EDTA solution (0.01 M)

until the initial wine red colour turned to blue (end point). The initial and final burette readings were recorded and total hardness was calculated.

Calcium hardness (mg/l)

It is determined based on titrating sample with EDTA in presence of specific indicator Murexide which reacts only with calcium ions in presence of magnesium ions.

Chemical Reagents

Sodium hydroxide solution (8%): 8g sodium hydroxide was dissolved in 100ml distilled water.

Murexide indicator: 0.2g ammonium purpurate and 100g of sodium chloride mixture was grinded.

EDTA solution (0.01N): Exactly 0.3723g EDTA was dissolved in 100ml distilled water.

Procedure

To a 50ml of sample taken in a 100ml conical flask, 1ml of Sodium hydroxide solution and a pinch of Murexide indicator were added. It was titrated against EDTA solution (0.01 M) until the initial pink colour turned to purple. The initial and final burette readings were recorded and calcium hardness was calculated.

Magnesium hardness (mg/l)

It was estimated by subtracting calcium hardness expressed as calcium carbonate from total hardness and multiplying with 0.244.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO, mg/l)

It is based on oxidation and reduction of manganous sulphate in the presence of dissolved oxygen and potassium iodide in acidic medium. This leads to the liberation of iodine equivalent to the original DO content of sample. The liberated Iodine is estimated by titrating it with sodium thiosulphate and starch as an indicator.

Chemical Reagents

Sodium Thiosulphate Solution (0.025 N): Exactly 6.205g sodium thiosulphate was dissolved in previously boiled distilled water and made up to 1 litre.

Manganous Sulphate Solution: Exactly 100g manganese sulphate was weighed and dissolved in 200ml of previously boiled distilled water and solution filtered.

Alkaline Potassium Iodide Solution: Exactly 100g potassium hydroxide and 50g potassium iodide was weighed and dissolved in 200ml of previously boiled distilled water.

Starch Indicator: Around 2g starch was dissolved in 100ml of warm distilled water.

Concentrated Sulphuric Acid: Commercially available.

Procedure (Winkler's Method)

A glass stopper BOD bottle of known volume (250-300ml) was taken and sample was filled without any bubbling by transferring through rubber tube and intense care was taken to avoid any bubbles in BOD bottle once the stopper was placed. To this 1ml each of manganese sulphate and potassium iodide solution was added. The bottles were kept as such till the precipitate was developed fully. To this 2ml of concentrated Sulphuric acid was added and the bottles were shaken thoroughly until the precipitate was fully dissolved. About 50ml of this solution was taken in a 100ml conical flask and titrated against Sodium Thiosulphate solution, until the initial blue colour turned to colourless using starch as an indicator. The initial and final burette reading were noted for DO estimation.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD, mg/l)

BOD is a measure of oxygen concentration in sample before and after incubation in dark at 20°C for 5 days or at 27°C for 3 days (APHA, 1992). It gives the relative amount of biologically degradable organic matter in the sample.

Chemical Reagents

All reagents used in determination of dissolved oxygen (DO) were used

Phosphate Buffer Solution: 3.34g $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.15g K_2HPO_4 , 0.8g KH_2PO_4 and 0.17g NH_4Cl was dissolved in distilled water to prepare 100ml of solution.

Magnesium Sulphate Solution: 8.25g magnesium sulphate was dissolved in distilled water to prepare 100ml of solution.

Calcium Chloride Solution: Exactly 2.75g anhydrous calcium chloride was dissolved in distilled water to prepare 100ml of solution.

Ferric Chloride Solution: 0.25g ferric chloride was dissolved in 100ml of distilled water.

Dilution water: About 1 litre of distilled water was aerated for half an hour and 1ml each of phosphate buffer solution, magnesium sulphate solution, calcium chloride solution, ferric chloride was added.

Procedure

The sample was diluted with dilution water (1:1 ratio) and transferred into BOD bottles. This was incubated at 27°C for three days in an incubator. The BOD bottles were taken out after three days and their dissolved oxygen (DO) content was determined immediately. The values were calculated by subtracting final DO from initial DO and expressed as mg/l.

Sulphate (mg/l)

Sulphate form Barium Sulphate crystals of uniform size by reacting with barium chloride in presence of acetic acid medium. The concentration of crystals is determined spectrophotometrically at wavelength 420nm.

Chemical Reagents

NaCl-HCl solution: About 240g sodium chloride was dissolved in distilled water. To this 20ml of Hydrochloric acid was added and made up to 1000ml solution using distilled water.

Glycerol-Ethanol solution: Glycerol and Ethanol was mixed up in 1:2 ratios.

Barium Chloride crystals: Commercially available.

Standard Sulphate solution: Exactly 0.1848g anhydrous Sodium Sulphate was dissolved in 250ml distilled water to give 500ppm of SO₄ stock solution. A range of standards was prepared by diluting it with distilled water.

Procedure

About 50ml filtered (Whatman No: 1) sample was taken in a 100ml conical flask and 10ml each of NaCl-HCl solution and Glycerol-Ethanol solution was added. To this about 0.15g Barium Chloride crystals were added and shaken. The absorbance of the solution was measured spectrophotometrically at 690nm. The standard Sulphate solutions were also processed in the similar manner, a standard curve was plotted between absorbance and concentrations of various standard solutions, and the result was expressed in mg SO₄/l.

Phosphate (mg/l)

Reactive Phosphorous is determined by treating it with Ammonium Molybdate to form molybdophosphoric acid and is then reduced by Stannous Chloride into intensely coloured Molybdenum blue. The formed colour is measured spectrophotometrically at 490nm.

Chemical Reagents

Ammonium Molybdate Solution: Exactly 2.5g Ammonium Molybdate was dissolved in 20ml of distilled water. To this 28ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added and diluted to 100ml with distilled water.

Stannous Chloride: Exactly 2.5g Stannous Chloride was dissolved in 100ml glycerol and heated on water bath (until complete dissolution occurred).

Standard Phosphate Solution: Exactly 0.14g Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate was dissolved in 100ml distilled water to give 1000ppm of PO₄ stock solution. A range of standards was prepared by diluting it with distilled water.

Procedure

About 10ml sample was taken in a 25ml standard measuring flask. To this 1ml of ammonium molybdate and 3 drops of stannous chloride were added. The contents were mixed well and volume was made up with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured spectrophotometrically at 690nm within 12-15 minutes after the development of blue colour. The standard phosphate solutions also processed in similar manner and the absorbance was noted for

each. A standard curve was plotted between absorbance and concentrations of various standard solutions. Estimated the value of phosphate in sample by comparing the absorbance of sample with the standard curve and the result was expressed in mg PO₄/L.

Ammonia (mg/l)

Ammonia forms Indophenols by reacting with hypochlorite and phenol, coloration is enhanced by nitroprusside. The colour intensity is measured spectrophotometrically at 640nm.

Chemical Reagents

Phenol Nitroprusside Solution: About 15g phenol was dissolved in 500ml of distilled water. To this 1 ml of freshly prepared 1.5% w/v aqueous solution of Sodium Nitroprusside was added

Alkaline Hypochlorite Solution: About 10g sodium hydroxide was dissolved in some distilled water and 2.7ml of 10% solution of hypochlorite was added. The volume was made up to 500ml by adding distilled water.

Standard Ammonium Chloride Solution: About 0.382g anhydrous Ammonium Chloride was dissolved in distilled water to make 100ml of solution. This stock solution contained 1g NH₄⁺-N/l (or 1.22g NH₃ /l). A range of standards was prepared by diluting it with distilled water.

Procedure

About 20ml filtered sample (Whatman No: 1) was taken in a 25ml volumetric flask. To this 2 ml each of Phenol Nitroprusside solution and Alkaline Hypochlorite solution was added. The volume was made up by adding ammonia-free distilled water. It was then kept in dark at 25°C temperature for an hour. The standards of different concentrations were prepared using ammonia free distilled water. The ammonia concentration was measured at 635nm spectrophotometrically. A standard curve was plotted between absorbance and concentrations of various standard solutions and the results were expressed in mg NH₄-N/l.

Nitrite (mg/l)

It is determined by measuring emittance at 543nm from azodye formed by coupling reaction between nitrite and α -(1 naphthyl)-ethlyene diamine dihydrochloride.

Chemical Reagents

EDTA Solution: About 0.5g of disodium salt of EDTA (Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid) was dissolved in distilled water to prepare 100 ml of solution.

Sulphanilic Acid Solution: About 0.6g Sulphanilic acid was dissolved in 70ml of warm distilled water. After cooling, 20ml of Hydrochloric acid (concentrated) was added, and the volume was made up to 100ml by distilled water.

α -Naphthylamine Hydrochloride Solution: About 0.6g α -Naphthylamine hydrochloride was taken in 100ml standard flask and dissolved in a little distilled water. To this 1ml of hydrochloric acid (concentrated) was added and the volume was made up to 100ml by distilled water.

Sodium Acetate Solution: About 27.2g Sodium Acetate was taken in a 100ml standard flask. The final volume was made up with distilled water.

Standard Nitrite Solution: Exactly 0.1232g Sodium Nitrite was taken in a 100ml standard flask and the volume was made up with distilled water. About 0.4ml of this solution was taken in a 100ml standard flask and diluted up to the mark. This gave a 100ml of stock solution having 1mg $\text{NO}_2\text{-N/l}$ (or 2.290mg NO_2 ions/l). The various standards were made ranging from 0.0 to 1.0ppm.

Procedure

Exactly 50ml of filtered sample was taken in an Erlenmeyer flask and 1ml of each EDTA solution, Sulphanilic acid and α -Naphthylamine hydrochloride solution was added. An appearance of wine red colour indicated the presence of nitrites. The absorbance was recorded on spectrophotometer at 520nm. Standard nitrite solutions were processed in the similar way. A standard curve was plotted between absorbance and concentrations of various standard solutions and the results were expressed in mg $\text{NO}_2\text{-N/l}$.

Chemical Reagents and Water

The chemical reagents used in the study were procured from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Division of GlaxoSmithKline Pharmaceuticals Limited, Mumbai, and were of analytical grade. The water used in the study was double distilled water prepared using Qualigens quartz double distillation assembly at SACON laboratory, Coimbatore

BIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

Benthic Macro Invertebrates Sampling and Identification

Benthic macro-invertebrate samples were collected in triplicates from littoral zones (depth 0-2 m) from 3 sites in each lake during February 2009 by using Van Veen's Grab sampler with surface area of 0.0318m². Sites were selected based on shallow muddy bottoms that could be well sampled by the sampler. From each benthic sampling site, water samples were also collected (as discussed above). Collected sediment from sampler was transferred into 20 litre plastic bucket and the sampler was rinsed with water. The sediment sample was made into suspension and was filtered through series of mesh from coarse metallic mesh to finer mesh of size 0.5mm. The organisms adhered to fine mesh and coarse mesh were collected and preserved in 4% formalin. The filtration was continued until no further organism in the sediment sample was found. The specimens were then collected, labeled and preserved. Taxonomic identification was done up to family level using taxonomic keys Edmondson 1959 and Mellanby 1938. The total number of individuals of each family were counted and recorded. The benthic macro-invertebrate community was assessed using six diversity indices,

Percentage Abundance of Family:

It is the ratio of number of individuals in a family to the total number of individuals in all the families (Sharma et. al., 2008). And the dominance (d) is only the ratio of number of individuals in a family to the total number of individuals in all the families.

$$\text{Abundance (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total number of individuals in family} \times 100}{\text{Total number of individuals in all the families}}$$

Family richness (S): It is the number of families occurring in a site.

Simpson's diversity index (D): The Simpson's diversity index (D) was calculated using the following equation (Simpson 1949):

$$D = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^s (p_i)^2$$

Where “ p_i ” is the proportion of individuals of the “ i^{th} ” taxon (Family) in the sample, and “ s ” is the total number of taxa in the sample. Simpson’s index gives relatively little weightage to the rare taxa and more weightage to the common taxa and ranges in value from 0 (low diversity) to a maximum of $(1-1/s)$.

Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index (H)

It is a widely used method for calculating biotic diversity in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, and is expressed as (Shannon and Weiner 1963):

$$H = - \sum_i^s (p_i)(\log_2 p_i)$$

Where,

H= index of species diversity

s= number of species

p_i = proportion of total sample belonging to the i^{th} species.

Evenness (J)

It is expressed as

$$J = \frac{H}{\log_{10} q}$$

Where H is the Shannon Wiener Diversity Index value and $\log_{10} q$ is the maximum H, the value of H when all species are equally abundant (Hill 1973), with q being the number of taxon in the sample.

Water Quality Index

It represents the quality of water in a single numerical value in subjective manner such as excellent, good, poor, very poor, unfit for drinking (Appendix 1, Mishra *et al.* 2008), etc. However, it is widely used for drinking water management purposes it can be compared with benthic community characteristics to gain a meaningful insight for pollution status of aquatic ecosystem.

It is based on recommendation of regulatory boards such as Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) and Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) considering the nine selected physico-chemical parameters of water viz., pH, dissolved oxygen, total dissolved solids, total hardness, calcium, magnesium, sulphate, chloride and nitrate. It is calculated by using the formula;

$$WQI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where,

q_i = Quality rating determined using formula

$$q_i = 100(v_i - v_{10}) / (s_i - v_{10})$$

where,

v_i = estimated value of n^{th} water quality parameter.

s_i = standard permissible limit of n^{th} parameter.

v_{10} = ideal value of the n^{th} parameter in pure water.

W_i = Unit weight factor (Appendix 2) for each parameter using formula

$$W_i = K / S_i$$

where,

K = proportionality constant

S_i = slandered value of i^{th} parameter.

Statistical analysis

To find the range, distribution and association of different parameters among themselves, basic descriptive statistics and 2-tail correlation matrix was performed on the analytical data using SPSS 11.0 (Norusis 1990). Multivariate test to assess variations of in the level of these parameters among the sites, and seasons was performed following the General Linear Model (GLM). The parameters were further examined with a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the SPSS 'FACTOR'. The factors were retained in the analysis based on the criterion that each retained factor had an Eigen value >1. Community diversity of the benthic macro invertebrates was calculated using the software 'Species diversity and richness (version 2.65)'.

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LAND USE CLASSIFICATION AND SPATIAL ANALYSIS

The general work steps carried out for Satellite imagery classification and spatial analysis was shown in (Figure 6)

Data Acquisition

The remote sensing data for land cover by NASA's Landsat TM for 1989 and Landsat ETM+ for 1999 was obtained from the Global Land Cover Facility (GLCF –<http://www.landcover.org/>), Institute for Advanced Computer Studies, University of Maryland, United States of America. The geographical area of Coimbatore was included in the world reference system path 155 and row 052 of Landsat imagery. The imagery of Landsat TM 1989 and Landsat ETM+ 1999 was downloaded and undergone for image analysis (Appendix 3). The imagery obtained as individual band wavelength was made into a single stack image comprising all seven bands, for the case of ETM+ the eighth band was omitted.

Image Analysis

The image analysis and processing of satellite imagery was carried out using the softwares Multispec W32 and ERDAS Imagine 8.5 (Adams and Gillespie 2006). The subset imagery of study area including geographical extent of four lakes of Coimbatore was prepared using Area of Interest tool and False Colour Composite (FCC) image was generated for the study area. The stacked and registered image was categorized into two step classification process: unsupervised classification and supervised classification. The signature file from unsupervised classification algorithm was edited using signature editor tool and then clusters were grouped into four land cover classes namely, urban, water body, bare land and vegetation. From this signature file the land cover was classified by supervised classification algorithm using Maximum Likelihood classifier. Land cover / land use summery included land class and its geographical area from attribute table of classified imagery including class and its geographical area.

Spatial Analysis

Vector generation and spatial analysis was carried out using Spatial Analyst Extension of Arc GIS 9.2 software. The classified image of study area was vectorised as Polygon feature for lakes extent and point features for urban areas using raster to vector tool in spatial analyst tool bar. The point features of urban area were used for density calculation and reclassification options in spatial analyst toolbar. The highest density urban area was vectorised using editor toolbar and analysed for Euclidian distance. The map generated from Euclidian distance analysis and layer of vectorised lakes canopy was stacked for generating degradation potential of lakes from urban centers.

Figure 6. Steps in land use classification and spatial analysis.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ASSESMENT

The Physico-chemical methods followed to assess the seasonal variations in water quality of the wetlands are discussed in the following paragraphs:

Hydrogen Ion Concentration (pH) and Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP, mV)

The pH was highest in Ukkadam lake in all the seasons (8.30 ± 0.24). The pH value for Chinnakulam was 7.89 ± 0.14 , Perur 7.8 ± 0.16 and Kurchi 7.78 ± 0.18 (Figure 7). For Perur the pH was in the order monsoon>post-monsoon>summer>winter, for Kurchi monsoon>post-monsoon>winter>summer, for Ukkadam summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon and for Chinnakulam post-monsoon>monsoon>winter>summer.

Figure 7. Seasonal variation in pH values for the lakes studied

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The Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP, mV) along with pH reflects the intensity factor of chemical constituents in water to react or mobilize (APHA 1992). ORP was high in the case of Ukkadam lake in all the seasons (-78.63 ± 14.3 mV). The ORP value for Chinnakulam was -51.2 ± 12.62 mV, for Perur -49.81 ± 7.76 mV and for Kurchi -47.03 ± 9.83 mV. The seasonal variation in ORP (Figure 8) for Perur was in the order of monsoon>summer>post-monsoon>winter, for Kurchi monsoon>post-monsoon >winter>summer, for Ukkadam summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon and for Chinnakulam post-monsoon>monsoon>winter>summer.

Figure 8. Seasonal variation in ORP (mV) values for the lakes studied

Electrical Conductivity (EC, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS, mg/l)

The Electrical Conductivity (EC, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) was highest in Ukkadam lake and was 2823.77 ± 1226.94 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ followed by Kurchi lake (546.43 ± 135.16 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), Chinnakulam lake (288.25 ± 88.34 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and Perur lake (238.16 ± 54.81 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). For Perur lake highest EC recorded among the seasons followed the order summer>winter>monsoon>post-monsoon,

for Kurchi lake summer>winter>monsoon>post-monsoon, for Ukkadam lake summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon and for Chinnakulam lake summer>winter>monsoon>post-monsoon (Figure 9). The similar trend was shown by Total Dissolved Solids (TDS, mg/l) and was highest in Ukkadam lake (1329.28±543.74 mg/l) followed by Kurchi lake (279.96±75.12 mg/l), Chinnakulam lake (149.2±40.06 mg/l) and Perur lake (127.2±32.41 mg/l).

Figure 9. Seasonal variation in EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) & TDS (mg/l) values for the lakes studied

Total Hardness (mg/l), Calcium Hardness (mg/l) and Magnesium Hardness (mg/l)

The recorded concentration of total hardness, calcium hardness and magnesium hardness for each lake and its seasonal variations is shown in Figure 10. Seasonal variation in total hardness (mg/l), calcium hardness (mg/l) and magnesium hardness (mg/l) values for the lakes studied. Total hardness was recorded highest in Ukkadam lake (217.13±26.27 mg/l) followed by Kurchi lake (215.33±18.49 mg/l), Perur lake (106.03±13.43 mg/l) and Chinnakulam lake (100.3±14.14 mg/l).

The seasonal variation in total hardness recorded from Perur lake was in the order summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon. However, for Kurchi lake, Ukkadam lake and Chinnakulam lake the trend was monsoon>summer>post-monsoon>winter, monsoon>post-monsoon>summer>winter and summer>post-monsoon>monsoon>winter, respectively. The highest recorded value and seasonal dynamics for calcium hardness was more or less the same as total hardness for all the lakes. In Perur it was 52.19 ± 14.08 mg/l, Kurchi 63.09 ± 28.79 mg/l, Ukkadam 99.13 ± 68.97 mg/l and Chinnakulam 56.92 ± 4.89 mg/l. On the contrary, magnesium hardness was high in Kurchi lake (37.14 ± 8.42 mg/l) followed by Ukkadam lake (28.79 ± 13.45 mg/l), Perur lake (13.13 ± 5.85 mg/l) and Chinnakulam lake (10.58 ± 3.08 mg/l).

Figure 10. Seasonal variation in total hardness (mg/l), calcium hardness (mg/l) and magnesium hardness (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

Chloride (mg/l) and Alkalinity (mg/l)

The recorded concentration of chloride and alkalinity for each lake and its seasonal variation is shown in Figure 11.

The chloride value, an indicator of sewage discharge pollution and human defecation was recorded high in Ukkadam lake (677.93 ± 197.45 mg/l) followed by Kurchi lake (78.71 ± 19.94 mg/l), Chinnakulam lake (54.28 ± 11.83 mg/l) and Perur lake (46.92 ± 19.43 mg/l). The similar trend was seen in alkalinity values. The alkalinity value for Ukkadam lake was 341.82 ± 95.85 mg/l, for Kurchi lake 187.07 ± 55.77 mg/l, for Chinnakulam lake 92.05 ± 11.91 mg/l and for Perur lake 61.13 ± 41.88 mg/l.

Figure 11. Seasonal variation in Chloride (mg/l) & Alkalinity (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

The seasonal variation in chloride for all the lakes was high and was in the order summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon. It is observed that Coimbatore has highest rainfall during post monsoon than monsoon season. However, in the case of Chinnakulam lake the order was summer>winter>post-monsoon>monsoon. Seasonal variation in alkalinity for Perur lake was winter>post-monsoon>monsoon>summer. For Kurchi lake and Ukkadam lake the trend was summer>winter>post-monsoon>monsoon.

The seasonal variation for Chinnakulam lake was post-monsoon>winter>summer>monsoon.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO, mg/l) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD, mg/l)

The Dissolved Oxygen (DO, mg/l) value and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD, mg/l) value for each lake and seasonal variation is shown in Figure 12. The DO value was high in Chinnakulam lake (6.51±0.96 mg/l) followed by Perur lake (6.32±0.89 mg/l), Ukkadam lake (5.87±0.7 mg/l) and Kurchi lake (4.86±1.32 mg/l). The BOD value was high in Ukkadam lake (3.85±0.47 mg/l) followed by Chinnakulam lake (3.37±1.77 mg/l), Perur lake (2.41±0.88 mg/l) and Kurchi lake (2.27±0.67 mg/l). The seasonal dynamics of BOD was same in the case of Ukkadam lake and Chinnakulam lake (summer>monsoon>winter>post-monsoon), in the case of Perur it was winter>summer>monsoon>post-monsoon and for Kurchi it was monsoon>summer>winter>post-monsoon.

Figure 12. Seasonal variation in DO (mg/l) & BOD (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

Phosphate (mg/l)

The phosphate value for each lake and its seasonal variation is shown in Figure 13. Phosphate value was highest in Chinnakulam lake (1.91 ± 2.12 mg/l) followed by Ukkadam lake (1.6 ± 1.74 mg/l), Kurchi lake (0.34 ± 0.34 mg/l) and Perur lake (0.269 ± 0.21 mg/l). The seasonal variation for phosphate for all the lakes was in the order of monsoon>summer>post-monsoon>winter.

Figure 13. Seasonal variation in Phosphate (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

Sulphate (mg/l)

The sulphate value for each lake with seasonal variation is shown in Figure 14. Sulphate value was highest in Ukkadam lake (68.52 ± 32.32 mg/l) followed by Kurchi lake (24.96 ± 7.017 mg/l), Chinnakulam lake (24.27 ± 16.91 mg/l), and Perur lake (11.44 ± 2.18 mg/l). The seasonal variation in sulphate for Perur, Kurchi, Ukkadam and Chinnakulam lake was in the order winter>post-monsoon>monsoon>summer, monsoon>summer>winter>post-monsoon, summer>monsoon>winter>post monsoon and monsoon>summer>winter>post monsoon, respectively.

Figure 14. Seasonal variation in Sulphate (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

Ammonia (mg/l) and Nitrite (mg/l)

The ammonia and nitrite value for each lake with seasonal variation is shown in Figure 15. The ammonia concentration was highest in Ukkadam lake (0.21 ± 0.08 mg/l) followed by Kurchi lake (0.111 ± 0.13 , mg/l), Chinnakulam lake (0.098 ± 0.08 , mg/l) and Perur lake (0.037 ± 0.02 , mg/l). In the case of nitrite, the concentration was highest in Ukkadam lake (0.091 ± 0.05 , mg/l) followed by Chinnakulam lake (0.064 ± 0.06 , mg/l), Perur lake (0.022 ± 0.008 , mg/l) and Kurchi lake (0.017 ± 0.011 , mg/l). The seasonal variation in ammonia concentration in Perur, Kurchi, Ukkadam and Chinnakulam was in the order monsoon>winter>post-monsoon>summer, winter>monsoon>summer>post-monsoon, post-monsoon>monsoon>winter>summer and monsoon>winter>summer>post-monsoon, respectively. For nitrite it was in the order monsoon>post-monsoon>summer>winter, summer>post-monsoon>monsoon>winter, summer>post-monsoon>winter>monsoon and monsoon>summer>postmonsoon>winter, respectively.

Figure 15. Seasonal variation in Ammonia (mg/l) and Nitrite (mg/l) values for the lakes studied.

The Pearson's correlation matrix (Two-tailed, $P < 0.05$) showed (Table 1) significant positive correlation of pH with EC, TDS, chloride and sulphate which may be attributed to the electrical properties of water such as salinity and osmotic pressure (Speies and Mitsch 2000), and electrometric method in determining the properties. Sulphate was positively correlated with EC, TDS, chloride and alkalinity. Chloride was also positively correlated with pH and EC thus, showing that EC and pH influence the salinity of water where chloride has an empirical relationship with salinity (Saxena 1987). Sulphate was positively correlated with pH, EC, TDS, chloride and alkalinity thus, inferring that in fresh water lakes reduced state of sulphur is influenced by pH and salinity of the water. The General Linear Model (GLM-Multivariate test, $P < 0.05$) performed showed that the concentrations of variables varied significantly among seasons and among sites with an exception of ammonia (GLM-Multivariate test, $P < 0.05$).

Table 1. Pearson's Correlation matrix of the select parameters of all lake

	PH	EC	TDS	TH	Cl ₂	Alk.	BOD	PO ₄	SO ₄	NO ₂
PH	1									
EC	0.964*	1								
TDS	0.962*	1*	1							
TH	NS	NS	NS	1						
Cl ₂	0.978*	0.998*	NS	NS	1					
ALK	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	1				
BOD	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	1			
PO ₄	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	1		
SO ₄	0.952*	0.981*	0.981*	NS	0.975*	0.953*	NS	NS	1	
NO ₂	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.996*	NS	NS	1

*: Significant (P<0.05), NS: Not Significant

The PCA performed in order to examine the variation patterns in the physico-chemical parameters (Table 2) resulted in 4 components, selected based on visual inspection of scree plots, which explained or accounted for 83% of the total variance. Table 3 shows that the first component accounted for 40.1% of the total variance in water characteristics among samples, reflecting the influence of the variables such as Cl₂, pH and EC. The second component, accounted for 15.5% of the total variance thus, reflecting the influence of the sulphate and BOD. The influence of ammonia concentration was reflected by the third component, which accounted for 15.2% of the total variance. The fourth component accounted for 12.2% of the total variance indicating the influence of water DO. Thus, the 4 PCA components can be characterized as ORP/Cl₂/pH/EC, SO₄/BOD, NH₄ and DO, respectively.

Table 2. PCA of water variables from the 4 lakes: factor loadings. Extraction method: Principal Component Analysis, Varimax rotation with Kaiser Normalisation (rotation converged in 13 iterations).

Parameters	Principal Components			
	I ORP/Cl ₂ /pH/EC	II PO ₄ /SO ₄ /BOD	III NH ₄	IV DO
pH (1)	0.885	0.127	-0.226	0.135
ORP (2)	-0.899	0.062	0.185	-0.18
EC (3)	0.878	0.243	0.334	-0.045
TDS (4)	0.877	0.224	0.348	-0.066
Total hardness (5)	0.437	0.035	0.607	-0.331
Cl ₂ (6)	0.887	0.207	0.324	-0.047
Alkalinity (7)	0.683	-0.104	0.573	-0.194
DO (8)	0.05	0.091	-0.145	0.943
BOD (9)	0.118	0.448	0.455	0.654
PO ₄ (10)	0.04	0.899	0.065	0.158
SO ₄ (11)	0.706	0.566	0.221	0.020
NH ₄ (12)	0.03	0.11	0.764	0.090
NO ₂ (13)	0.335	0.335	0.024	-0.181
Total loading ^A	5.206	2.015	1.977	1.59
% Variance explained	40.047	15.501	15.207	12.228
^A Sums of squared loadings				

Table 3. The Eigen values and percentage variance of PCA output.

Axis	Eigen value	% Variance	Cumulative variance	% variance of broken stick model
1	5.206	40.047	40.047	24.2
2	2.015	15.501	55.548	16.7
3	1.977	15.507	70.755	12.9
4	1.59	12.228	82.983	10.3

From the percentage variables (Table 3) of broken stick model for 13 variables it was worthwhile to examine the first axis where % variance was more than broken stick distribution (Shaw 2003). It was expected that all other axis having % variance less than broken stick distribution were random noises. The scatter plot diagram drawn by taking the PCA output of first two axes is shown in Figure 16. Eigen vector loadings for first axis was weighted towards chloride (6), pH (1), Electrical conductivity (3), TDS (4) with single negative loading for ORP (2).

From the scatter diagram, Eigen vector value of chloride, pH electrical conductivity and TDS was clumped together showing a relationship between these parameters along a negative Eigen value with ORP. All other variables were relatively scattered all over the axis and inferred no relationship among them.

Figure 16. Scatter diagram of first two Principle axis of PCA output.

BIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

Benthic macro invertebrates

Water Quality Index (Harkins 1974; Mishra *et al.* 2008) calculated for each lake showed that Ukkadam lake was the most highly polluted amongst the lakes studied (WQI=123) followed by Kurchi lake (WQI=97), Chinnakulam lake (WQI=84) and Perur lake (WQI=75). The littoral benthic macro-invertebrates collected from these lakes (Table 4) comprised of four Phyla viz., Annelids, Arthropods, Crustaceans and Mollusks. Few families could not be identified and there identification is in process. Highest number of taxon was recorded from Kurchi lake (17 families) followed by Perur lake (14 families), Chinnakulam lake (14 families) and Ukkadam lake (13 families). Family percentage abundance for Perur lake (Figure 17), Kurchi lake (Figure 18),

Ukkadam lake (Figure 19) and Chinnakulam lake (Figure 20), and diversity indices (Table 5) varied among each lake.

Table 4. Number of organisms per m² recorded in each family from each lake.

Class	Order	Family	Perur	Kurchi	Ukkadam	Chinnakulam
Annelida	Oligochaeta	Tubificidae	157	178	1625	105
	Hirudinea	Glossiphoniidae	0	0	7	0
Insecta	Diptera	Culcidae	35	10	101	17
		Anisoptera	Libellulidae	17	10	56
		Gomphidae	0	3	0	10
	Ephemeroptera	Tricorythidae	122	0	0	49
		Siphonuridae	0	3	0	3
		Heptagenidae	3	3	0	0
	Coleoptera	Dytiscidae	21	0	31	3
		Cruculionidae	0	0	0	17
		Hydrophilidae	3	35	10	0
	Hemiptera	Nepidae	28	0	7	0
		Notonectidae	0	7	0	0
Corixidae		52	35	0	0	
Pelidae		42	14	3	0	
Naucoridae		0	0	10	0	
Zygoptera	Agrionidae	10	17	101	14	
Plecoptera	Plecoptera*	3	3	14	17	
Crustacea	Amphipod	Haustoriidae	0	7	0	0
	Ostracoda	Ostracoda*	0	24	0	10
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Planorbidae	42	31	129	21
		Lymnaeidae	3	154	3	34
		Gastropoda*	0	24	0	28

*: Identification could not be done and are under process.

Table 5. Diversity indices of benthic samples recorded from the lakes sampled

Index	Perur Lake	Kurchi Lake	Ukkadam Lake	Chinnakulam Lake
S	14	17	13	14
D	6.0061	5.1608	2.0823	6.9807
H	2.0771	2.0636	1.2141	2.2531
J	0.78705	0.72835	0.47335	0.85376
D	0.29182	0.319	0.6750	0.30347
WQI	75	97	123	84

S: Number of families per lake S; D: Simpson's diversity Index; H: Shannon Wiener's diversity index; J: Evenness; D: Dominance; WQI: Water Quality Index

Perur lake % abundance

Figure 17. Percentage abundance of benthic macro-invertebrates in Perur lake.

kurchi lake % abundance of benthos

Figure 18. Percentage abundance of benthic macro-invertebrates in Kurchi lake.

Figure 19. Percentage abundance of benthic macro-invertebrates in Ukkadam lake.

Figure 20. Percentage abundance of benthic macro-invertebrates in Chinnakulam lake.

LAND USE CLASSIFICATION AND SPATIAL ANALYSIS

The false colour composite image of study area was shown in (Figure 21). The classified image of land use for study area during 1989 and 1999 is shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23. It was observed that during 1989 the urban area was about 486.4 hectares and during 1999, it was about 735.9 hectares (Table 6). The non-urban area comprising water body, vegetation, bare land was about 3373.8 hectares during 1989 and 3124.2 hectares during 1999. It is thus, inferred that in a decade the urban area was increased to about 51.2% in the study area and non-built up area had decreased by 7.3% (Table 6).

Figure 21. FCC (False Colour Composite) image of Landsat TM (1989) and Landsat ETM+ (1999) of study area.

Table 6. Land use of study area during 1989 and 1999.

Land use	1989 (Hectares)	1999 (Hectares)	Percentage change
Urban	486.4	735.9	+51.2
Non Urban	3373.8	3124.2	-7.3

Figure 22. Land use classification of study area 1989.

Figure 23. Land use classification of study area 1999.

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Degradation potential from Urban centers 1999

Figure 24. Degradation map of lakes from urban centers.

The degradation map generated (Figure 24) by spatial analysis 1999 imagery shows that Ukkadam lake has more number of urban pockets in its immediate vicinity and is likely to be highly degraded. In the case of Kurchi lake the urban pockets are relatively far from lakes riparian showing that low degradation levels than Ukkadam lake. The urban pockets were relatively far in the case of rest other lakes thus, showing least degradation levels for Perur and Chinnakulam lake.

Chapter 5.

DISCUSSION

The high value of pH and ORP in Ukkadam lake in comparison with others show high pollution loads in Ukkadam lake from industrial effluents. Industrial effluents such as dyeing industries contain high quantity of alkalis (Dara 1993) as waste and thus might have lead to high pH levels in the Ukkadam lake. The present recorded pH values of Ukkadam lake were much higher to the pH values reported by Mohanraj *et al.* (2000). The TDS values exceeded the (WHO 1997) permissible limits of 1000 mg/l in Ukkadam lake and during summer it was twice double the value reported by Mohanraj *et al.* (2000). Senthilnathan and Azeez (1999) state that industrial effluents from dyeing and bleaching industries have high salt content and can be a possible cause for the high values of TDS in Ukkadam lake. High TDS leads to high density and thus increases the osmotic pressure (Anitha 2005). The chloride values were high in Ukkadam lake and exceeded the (WHO 1997) permissible limit of 250mg/l. The high chloride values are attributed to the human defecation practices in the vicinity of the wetland and industrial effluents discharge. Similar increase was recorded for alkalinity during the post-monsoon season in the case of Chinnakulam lake. The increased levels of alkalinity in Chinnakulam lake may be due to the possible leaching of pollutants from the Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) in the adjacent area.

Phosphate level was high in Chinnakulam lake which may be attributed to the usage of Diammonium Phosphate (DAP) fertilizers in farm house and agricultural lands in the adjoining areas. The high levels of phosphate may also be attributed to the animal waste present in and around the water bodies. Ukkadam lake is located besides one of the biggest fish market of the city and many slaughter houses are present in its immediate vicinity. The sulphate value was highest in Ukkadam lake which might be attributed to the sewage discharge joining this lake. The high ORP and sulphate value leads to the favorable condition for sulphate to get reduced chemically or biologically through action of sulphur reducing bacteria and thus, leading to the production of highly toxic Hydrogen Sulphide (H₂S) gas (Anitha 2005). This might be a probable reason for the complete absence of benthic macro-invertebrates in the profoundal zones of Ukkadam lake.

The waters of the four lakes studied are mainly used for irrigation purposes. Their polluted condition is of serious concern and poses considerable impact on aquatic biota, public health and ground water quality. The river Noyyal during rainy season gets flooded and during lean months it carries enormous amount of sewage and other waste material thus, affecting the water quality of these wetlands. As hinted above, the deterioration of the lakes was mostly caused due to the discharge of effluent from industries like dyeing, jewellery making, foundries, urban sewage and municipal solid waste dumping. Much of the lakes boundaries are used for dumping house hold garbage. These wetlands provide the city with valuable ecosystem services and goods and their conservation is essential for the city scape and the population in the area. High nutrient input due to several reasons has led to the increased growth of water hyacinth '*E. crassipes*'. For the conservation of these wetlands regular water quality monitoring, control of weed growth, stopping dumping of solid wastes, clearing the encroachments and prevention of release of untreated effluents and sewage is necessary. Treatment of the effluents before being discharged into the lakes and creation of waste stabilization ponds in the vicinity of lakes are likely to reduce the impacts of these effluents. Establishment of buffer area around the lakes as protected sites especially in the case of Perur and Ukkadam which are potential bird habitats would reduce the anthropogenic pressures and augment the natural purification processes in these systems and improve the environmental quality of the wetland.

Most diversity indices are based on underlying principle that undisturbed communities will have a high species richness and diversity (Metcafe 1989). It is known that Shannon Wiener diversity index in the range of >3.0 reflects healthy environment and in the range of 2-3 reflects moderately healthy and <1 shows heavily degraded environment (Jhingran 1987; Khan *et al.* 2004). The measure of Shannon Wiener's diversity index and Simpson's diversity index which were more appropriate in aquatic ecosystems (Washington 1984). Ukkadam lake showed minimum diversity. However, the dominance was maximum dominance which can be attributed to high pollution loads. Highest percentage abundance was for the family Tubificidae (68%) in Ukkadam lake thus, inferring that low DO, high EC, TDS make considerable impact on the survival of the sensitive benthic invertebrates thus, resulting in the changes in the community composition and abundances

(Growth *et al.* 1992; Collier 1995; Kawai *et al.* 1996; Spieles and Mitsch 2000). It is also inferred that the impact of chloride pollution which was highest in Ukkadam lake supported pollution tolerant macro-invertebrate families such as Tubificidae (Nijboer 2004). Another high pollution tolerant family Hirudina (Mandaville 2002) was recorded only from this lake. The water quality of all three lakes was very poor thus, comprising different community composition. Kurchi lake which is having high WQI among these three lakes supported highest number of taxon abundant in pollution tolerant families like Tubificidae and Lymnaeidae (Mandaville 2002). The weed infestation 'water hyacinth' makes considerable reduction in DO. But the large water area dominated by different plant communities makes this lake favorable for different taxa such as the family Amphipod (recorded only from this lake). The occurrence of a high pollution tolerant family (Tubificidae) along with a sensitive family (Tricorythidae) indicates the location specific pollution loadings. The family Tubificidae was recorded from sites being used for regular washing and bathing. On the contrary, Tricorythidae (low pollution tolerant family) was recorded from relatively cleaner waters. Chinnakulam lake showed highest value for diversity indices and high evenness in community composition for benthic macro-invertebrates thus, indicating that the water shed area of this lake was apparently less disturbed. Though the lake is being degraded by municipal solid waste the benthic community was found to be relatively balanced. It may be attributed to the low imperviousness riparian in the Chinnakulam lake.

Satellite imagery such as Landsat satellite multi-spectral, multi-temporal remote sensing images is a promising technique for urbanization analysis (Huyang and Fipps 2006). Land use classification of multi-temporal data revealed 50% increase in the urban area within a decade (1989-1999). Hence, it is obvious to believe that the study area will get much more urbanized in next few years. Studies by Booth and Jackson (1997) elsewhere, state that 10% effective impervious area in the watershed of aquatic ecosystems will lead to a probable irreversible loss in its functioning. Density analysis in the present study predicts only the highest density raster point as urban point features and lacks in revealing the actual area which can be an industrial area or a house hold or a commercial area. The Euclidean distance provides only the generalized view / relationship between urban centre and lake.

The map generated from Landsat imagery spatial analysis (Figure 24) is based on this generalization. From the map it is evident that Ukkadam lake has highest degradation potential zones from urban centers and the same is reflected from the physico-chemical and biological assessment. The degradation zones (Euclidean distance between lakes and urban centres) in Kurchi was recorded slightly smaller than the Ukkadam lake. However, the extent of degradation in the case of Kurchi as recorded from physico-chemical analysis and biological assessment did not show similar trend as shown in the case of Ukkadam lake. Hence, it is concluded that there are several other factors leading to there degradation. For example, the absence of direct industrial effluents and sewage discharges and partial usage of the area for defecation practices and MSW must have contributed to the low degradation extent in the case of Kurchi. The lake Kurchi, is known to hold a good diversity of flora and fauna though its major portion of water shed is covered with *Eichhornia crassipes*. Hence, it is imperative to look into underlying factors leading to the well being of Kurchi lake which would help devising management strategies and reducing impacts of urban centers on other aquatic ecosystems.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that Ukkadam lake is the most degraded lake amongst the studied lakes, followed by Kurchi lake, Perur lake and Chinnakulam lake. There is obvious trend shown from physical, chemical and biological methods that lake in the immediate vicinity of urban centers suffered from relatively high degradation level. From the spatio-temporal analysis using Landsat imagery it was found that the urban area in the vicinity of lakes has increased to above 50% in past a decade. Thus, in due course of time all the lakes are likely to face a similar kind of degradation. Thus, monitoring plans for the immediate conservation and mitigation measures of these lakes need to be implemented.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Water quality rating for drinking purposes.	
Index value (WQI)	Water quality rating
0-25	Excellent
26-50	Good
51-75	Poor
76-100	Very poor
>100	Unfit for drinking

Appendix 2. Drinking water standards recommending agencies and unit weight (all values except pH in mg/l)				
Sl. No	Properties	Standards (S _i)	Recommending Agency	Unit Weight (w _i)
1	pH	6.5-8.5	ICMR and BIS	0.219
2	TDS	500	ICMR and BIS	0.003708
3	DO	0.5	ICMR	0.37
4	Total hardness	500	ICMR and BIS	0.00618
5	Calcium	75	ICMR and BIS	0.02472
6	Magnesium	30	ICMR and BIS	0.0618
7	Sulphate	150	ICMR and BIS	0.01236
8	Chloride	250	ICMR and BIS	0.007416
9	Nitrate	45	ICMR and BIS	0.0412

Appendix 3. Details of Satellite Imagery downloaded form GLCF (Jensen 2000)			
Sl. No	Characteristics	Imagery I (1989)	Imagery II(1999)
1	Sensor platform	Landsat TM	Landsat ETM+
2	Date of acquisition	21/11/1989	09/11/1999
3	Path and Row of study area	155 and 52	155 and 52
4	Reference System	WRS 2	WRS 2
5	Product type	Orthorectified	Orthorectified
6	Total sensor band numbers	7	8
	Band Spectral Resolution	0.45-0.52	
	Band 1 (µm)	0.52-0.60	0.450-0.515
	Band 2 (µm)	0.63-0.69	0.525-0.605
	Band 3 (µm)	0.76-0.90	0.630-0.690
	Band 4 (µm)	1.55-1.75	0.750-0.900
	Band 5 (µm)	10.40-12.5	1.55-1.75
	Band 6 (µm)	2.08-2.35	10.40-12.50
	Band 7 (µm)	-	2.08-2.35
	Band 8 (µm)		
7	IFOV at nadir	30X30m for Bands 1 to 5, 7 120X120 m for band 6	0.52-0.90 30X30 m for bands 1 to 5,7 60X60 m for band 6 15X15 m for band 8

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